

FEASIBILITY STUDY OF A SANDWICH CHOPPER DISC FOR A TIME OF FLIGHT (TOF) SPECTROMETER

Valeria Antonelli¹, Matthias Weinzierl¹ and Horst Baier¹

¹Institute of Lightweight Structures, Technische Universität München
Boltzmannstr. 15, 85748 Garching, Germany
Email: antonelli@tum.de, web page: <http://www.llb.mw.tum.de>

Keywords: Finite Element, Manufacturing, Modal Analysis, Structural Design

ABSTRACT

The Institute of Lightweight Structures of the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering of the Technische Universität München has been designing and producing CFRP chopper discs for over a decade, specializing in designs of light discs with a high rotational speed. Chopper discs are commonly used in neutron “Time-of-Flight” (TOF) spectroscopy. They are discs with one or more apertures rotating around an axis parallel to the neutron beam, reaching operational speeds of up to 22,000 rpm. The driving design requirements are the operational speed and the maximum allowable weight. For instruments requiring a low operational speed, it is possible to design very light CFRP discs. An ultralight chopper disc, however, frequently implies instability: with its natural frequencies being very low, the disc is prone to oscillations during both acceleration to and deceleration from the operational speed. In contrast, a dynamically stable disc reacts directly, also in the case of an abrupt stop, and can be better controlled. Ideally, therefore, the natural frequency of the disc needs to be higher than its operational speed. This additional requirement makes it necessary to increase the weight of the disc. This paper presents the feasibility study of a sandwich chopper disc, with the aim of maximizing its natural frequency and reducing the weight penalty caused by a solid CFRP disc with the same natural frequency. The structural design of such a disc is presented as well as the manufacturing steps that lead to the manufacturing of a prototype.

1 INTRODUCTION

Chopper discs are used in “Time of Flight” (TOF) techniques [1, 2]. The Time of Flight spectrometer utilizes a cascade of chopper discs to produce a pulsed monochromatic neutron beam, which then impinges on the sample. From the time-of-flight from sample to detector, the neutron energy after the scattering is determined.

Chopper discs (Figure 1) are circular discs with a central circular cutout, through which the rotating shaft is fixed. The outer part of the disc has one or more apertures, or “windows”. The outer area of the disc is coated with a neutron absorbing material, typically ¹⁰B. The disc rotates in a housing with a vacuum. The rotational speed of the disc mainly defines the length of the pulse that hits the sample.

Current state-of-the-art chopper discs have a maximal operating speed of 22,000 rpm and an outer diameter of 750 mm maximum (independent of the number of apertures and their dimension). Not every chopper disc is rotating at a large operational speed nor does it have large windows, therefore most of the existing chopper discs are made of metal, due to the easier design and lower production costs. Only the largest and fastest chopper discs are made of CFRP, due to their higher relative stiffness compared to metal.

CFRP chopper discs have several advantages with respect to metal ones: they are lighter than their equivalent metal ones, they have a longer operational life, need less frequent inspection and the absorber coating is more easily applied. These advantages make the use of CFRP chopper discs attractive also for slow rotating discs when, for example, weight plays an important role. The weight of the disc, in fact, influences the power of the engine and its components that allow for the rotation of the disc.

Figure 1: Example of a CFRP chopper disc with two symmetrical windows.

In the case of ultra-light chopper discs, an important design parameter is the stability of the disc. In general, the disc is designed in such a way that the natural frequencies of the disc are far above its maximum rotational frequency during operation. The spectrometers, on the other hand, can generally operate at any speed below the maximum operating one; therefore, it is preferable to have the natural frequencies of the disc over the maximum rotational frequency during operation in order to have a vibration-free disc within the range of testing speeds.

2 LARGE CHOPPER DISCS

In general, the driving design mechanism for a chopper disc is its strength; therefore, its weight is minimized taking into account the allowable strength at ultimate load. In the case of a chopper disc with a low rotational speed and a large diameter, stability starts playing a more important role. In order to turn a lightweight solid disc into a stable one, additional mass needs to be added. This, however, causes additional centrifugal forces which may have a negative impact on the strength of the disc.

Modern neutron research centers [3] are long pulse spallation sources in which most instruments will rely on time-of-flight technique. For this purpose a multitude of different chopper devices is needed, all with different requirements concerning diameter and rotational speed. In particular, a number of instruments will be located at long distances from the source of neutron production. Advanced neutron guide systems, transporting the neutrons to the instrument, require rather large dimensions. The diameter of the disc, which has to accommodate the apertures needed to monochromatise the pulse of the neutron beam, might therefore increase to more than 1000 mm [4]. For such a disc, stability becomes an additional parameter in the design.

2.1 Effect of the absorber weight

Due to the large windows, the area covered with the boron coating will be significant. In the present design, the boron coating is placed on the outer diameter of the discs around the windows as can be seen in Figure 2. This coating has a significant influence on the natural frequencies of the disc: high masses on the outer diameter, in fact, make the natural frequencies decrease. Furthermore, this mass, due to its poor mechanical properties, does not add any stiffness to the disk.

In the case of deep apertures, the boron occupies a large part of the disk and has a substantial influence on the inertial load applied to the structure. In this case it is more effective if the boron is placed between the CFRP layers instead of being coated on the outside. The natural frequencies, in fact, increase by more than 40%.

Figure 2 gives an overview of the procedure described above. For apertures that are 15% of the disc's radius, the boron layer as a coating decreases the natural frequencies by 30%. A boron core is of interest

for all discs with a boron coverage higher than 20 % of its radius, and it is advised for all discs with apertures whose length is more than 40 % of its radius. This new manufacturing method might be an appropriate procedure to increase the natural frequencies without changing the weight of the disc and the stiffness properties.

Figure 2: Natural frequencies versus radial coverage of boron.

3 CASE STUDY

A typical example of a chopper disc whose main design parameter is its stability is shown in Figure 3. Its ultimate speed requirement was, given by the physical scientist, 250 Hz, equivalent to 15,000 rpm. It is one of the largest disc ever manufactured in CFRP, with an outer diameter of 750 mm, but very small windows and a relatively low operational speed. The requirements allowed for a design of an ultralight disc, with a weight of less than 2 kg and a maximal thickness of lower 10 mm. The first five natural frequencies of the ultralight disc, though, laid below the operational speed, the first one being only 33 Hz. The design was therefore modified to the one shown in Figure 3, where the weight increased to 5 kg in order to obtain a first completely symmetrical mode of about 130 Hz, still below the operational speed, but controllable.

Figure 3: Sketch and CAD drawing of the manufactured disc, including the hub.

In order to verify the calculations, the disc was tested experimentally. The experimental set-up and the natural frequencies in the range of interest are shown in Figure 4. The disc, without its shaft, was softly suspended on a balancing spring with a frequency of about 1 Hz in case of a centrally positioned (i.e. close to the hub) accelerometer. Two tests were carried out. In the first one, the excitation was on the edge of the disc, as well as the accelerometer. In the second one, both accelerometer and hammer excitation were close to the center. The natural frequencies measured in a spectrum between 80 Hz and

180 Hz are shown in Table 1. The conclusion of the experimental analysis was consistent with the numerical one, confirming the reliability of the calculations.

Figure 4 Experimental modal analysis of the manufactured disc.

Modes	Lateral excitation	Central excitation
1	105.75 Hz	105.75 Hz
2	109.75 Hz	109.75 Hz
3	128.50 Hz	128.50 Hz
4	135.00 Hz	
5	176.25 Hz	

Table 1: Spectrum in the range of 80-180 Hz.

4 SANDWICH DESIGN

In the case study shown above, it appeared evident that in order to keep an ultra-light chopper disc stable it is necessary to increase its weight. The addition of weight to a disc, though, is in most of the cases extremely counterproductive with respect to the stresses such a disc needs to sustain. It leads, in most cases to a reduction of the requirements in terms of either stability or rotational forces. The ideal solution would be an increase of bending stiffness that does not increment the weight in such a substantial way. A sandwich construction is therefore the ideal option, especially in the case described above, where the small windows allow for an increase of bending stiffness in almost the complete disc, so that the thickness in the window area is kept low, without reducing the accuracy of the measurements desired by the scientist.

The specific case allowed for the design of a disc with a constant core thickness of 25 mm and the same thickness of the facings considered for the case of the ultra-light disc, for a total weight of less than 3.5 kg. Being the first critical natural frequency 350 Hz, the sandwich disc is stable up to its ultimate speed.

Figure 5: CAD rendering of the sandwich disc.

The current production technique for chopper disc uses carbon fibre pre-preg, hardened in an autoclave between two steel molds to obtain the best performances in terms of fibre volume content and outer shape. In the present feasibility study, the same production technique is envisioned for the sandwich chopper discs. For the facings, the same material used for the solid CFRP disc was considered, namely M30SC carbon fibres with an epoxy resin [4]. For the core, a high performance structural foam, AIREX R82.60 was chosen [6]. This is a closed-cell, thermoplastic polymer foam with an extremely high strength-to-weight ratio which can be used with pre-preg processing at operating temperatures above the current manufacturing process.

Figure 6 shows the results of the FE-Analyses of the analysed case. The modal analysis shows that the expected critical mode occurs far above the ultimate speed of the disc. The thin outer ring of the disc, which is a solid CFRP laminate, does not influence the global behaviour. In the same way, the structural analysis shows a very stiff disc with much localised stress concentrations around the windows. The maximal stresses are well below those allowables, giving a good reserve factor in the disc design.

Figure 6: Results of respectively modal (left) and static analysis (right).

5 CONCLUSIONS

A sandwich chopper disc was designed, with the purpose of increasing the critical frequency without a large weight penalty. It was shown that the addition of a core with a constant thickness of 25 mm allowed for an increase of the critical frequency of an order of magnitude, so that it occurred at a speed higher than the operational one with less than twice as much weight.

Disc	Weight	Critical Frequency
<i>Ultra-light CFRP</i>	1.98 Kg	33.41 Hz
<i>Solid CFRP</i>	4.56 Kg	130.10 Hz
<i>Sandwich</i>	3.38 Kg	351.92 Hz

Table 2 Comparisons between the different discs.

In Table 2, comparisons among the analysed configurations is presented. The use of a solid CFRP disc has the disadvantage of a large weight increase, which is counterproductive in terms of mass that needs to be accelerated and therefore of occurring stresses. A sandwich copper disc is also more effective and cheaper in terms of raw material used.

REFERENCES

- [1] J.R.D.Copley and T.J. Udovic “Neutron Time-of-Flight Spectroscopy” *Journal of Research of the National Institute of Standards and Technologies*, Vol. 98, No1, pp 71-87, 1993.
- [2] Antonelli V, Wedekind M, Kämer L, Baier H, “The Design of a CFRP Chopper Disk for a Time of Flight Spectrometer”, ICCM 18, 2011, Korea.
- [3] <http://europenspallationsource.se>.
- [4] Antonelli V, Lohstroh W, Baier H, “Feasibility Study of a Large Chopper Disc for a TOF Spectrometer”, ICCM 19, 2013, Montreal, Canada
- [5] Weinzierl M, Schatz M, Antonelli V, Baier H, „ A study of the Structural Dynamic of CFRP Chopper Disks”, Sampe SETEC, 2014
- [6] Airex® BaltekR82 technical data sheet.